

Supplementary Material for

The rediscovery of a relict unlocks the first global phylogeny of whip spiders (Amblypygi)

Gustavo S. de Miranda*, Siddharth S. Kulkarni*, Jéssica Tagliatela, Caitlin M. Baker, Alessandro P.L. Giupponi, Facundo M. Labarque, Efrat Gavish-Regev, Michael G. Rix, Leonardo S. Carvalho, Livia Maria Fusari, Mark S. Harvey, Hannah M. Wood, Prashant P. Sharma

This PDF file includes:

Supplementary Methods.

Supplementary Tables S1-S6.

Supplementary Table S1. Extant diversity of phylogenetic relicts within Chelicerata that constitute sister groups to extant orders.

Supplementary Table S2. Locality and accession data for terminals included in the study. Nuclear histone 3, H3; mitochondrial cytochrome c oxidase subunit I, COI; nuclear 28S rDNA, 28S; nuclear 18S rDNA, 18S; mitochondrial 16S rDNA, 16S; mitochondrial 12S rDNA, 12S.

Supplementary Table S3. Fossil calibrations and references for divergence time estimation.

Supplementary Table S4. Concatenation of UCE and six-marker data set.

Supplementary Table S5. Area coding scheme used for biogeographic analysis.

Supplementary Table S6. Statistics of model comparison inferred from the RASP analysis.

Supplementary Table S7. Likelihood percentages of inferred ancestral areas using RASP. Area coding as follows: Nearctic-A; Oriental-B; Neotropical-C; Africa-D; Australasia-E; Mediterranean-F; Sundaland-G.

Supplementary Figures S1-S5.

Supplementary Figure S1. Maximum likelihood phylogenies reconstructed using ultraconserved elements using Blended probe set (a-d) and Spider2Kv1 probe set (e-h) at occupancies 1% (a, e), 10% (b, f), 25% (c, g) and 40% (d, h).

Supplementary Figure S2. Sensitivity of age estimates of Amblypygi with *Paracharon* fossil. Median node ages inferred by MCMCTree (top) and LSD2 (bottom), upon retention or exclusion of Paracharontidae.

Supplementary Figure S3. Biogeographic analysis of Amblypygi with *Paracharon* coded as Neotropical+Africa. Pie charts at nodes indicate probability of individual or a combination of ancestral areas. Area coding as follows: Nearctic-A; Oriental-B; Neotropical-

C; Africa-D; Australasia-E; Mediterranean-F; Sundaland-G.

Supplementary Figure S4. Biogeographic analysis of *Amblypygi* using DEC model. Pie charts at nodes indicate probability of individual or a combination of ancestral areas. Nearctic-A; Oriental-B; Neotropical-C; Africa-D; Australasia-E; Mediterranean-F; Sundaland-G.

Supplementary Figure S5. Divergence time estimates optimized by MCMCTree and LSD2 using fossil-based node calibrations. Conventions of HPD intervals follow the bottom legend.

Supplementary Figure S6. Biogeographic analysis of *Amblypygi* using DEC+j model with the exclusion of *Paracharon*. Pie charts at nodes indicate probability of individual or a combination of ancestral areas. Nearctic-A; Oriental-B; Neotropical-C; Africa-D; Australasia-E; Mediterranean-F; Sundaland-G.

Supplementary Methods

Species

Sampling

Specimens sequenced for this study were hand-collected from field sites or contributed by museum collections of the National Museum of Natural History, the Smithsonian Institution, Washington, DC, USA (USNM); the Museum of Comparative Zoology, USA (MCZ); the Natural History Museum of Denmark, Copenhagen (NHMD); the Queensland Museum, Brisbane, Australia (QMB). the Museu Nacional do Rio de Janeiro, Brazil (MNRJ); the California Academy of Sciences, San Francisco, USA (CAS); the State Museum of Natural History Stuttgart, Germany (SNMS); the Western Australian Museum (WAM), and the Universidade Federal do Piauí, Brazil (CHNUFPI).

Library preparation for ultraconserved element sequencing

The homogenate from DNA extraction was incubated at 55 °C overnight and purified following the manufacturer's protocol. The DNA extractions were quantified using high sensitivity Qubit fluorometry (Life Technologies, Inc.) and quality checked using gel electrophoresis on a 1.5% agarose gel.

Depending on prior degradation and quality of the DNA, between 7 and 100 ng of DNA were sheared between 10 and 60 s (amp=25%, pulse=10–10 seconds, to a target size of approximately 250–600 bp) by sonication (Q800R, Qsonica Inc.). Sheared DNA was dried completely and rehydrated to the required input volume (13 µL) and used as input for DNA library preparation (Kapa Hyper Prep Library kit, Kapa Biosystems). After ligation of universal stubs (Faircloth and Glenn, 2012), a 0.8× SPRI bead clean was done (Kapa Pure Beads, Kapa Biosystems) on a Wafergen Apollo liquid handler (Wafergen Biosystems), resulting in 30 µL of post-ligation library. For adapter ligation, we used TruSeq-style

adapters (Faircloth and Glenn, 2012). PCR conditions were as follows: 15 μ L post ligation library, 25 μ L HiFi HotStart polymerase (Kapa Biosystems), 2.5 μ L each of Illumina TruSeq- style i5 and i7 primers, and 5 μ L double-distilled water (ddH₂O). We used the following thermal protocol (Kapa Biosystems): 98 °C for 45 s; 13 cycles of 98 °C for 15 s, 65 °C for 30 s, 72 °C for 60 s, and final extension at 72 °C for 5 m. PCR cleanup was done with a 0.8 X SPRI bead clean (Kapa Pure Beads, Kapa Biosystems) on a Wafergen Apollo (TaKaRa Bio Inc. USA) with a final library volume of 20 μ L. Following clean-up, libraries were divided into enrichment pools containing eight libraries combined at equimolar ratios with final concentrations of 137–184 ng/ μ L.

Hybridization reactions were incubated for 24 h at 65 °C, subsequently, all pools were bound to streptavidin beads (MyOne C1; Life Technologies), and washed. We combined 15 μ L of streptavidin bead-bound, washed, enriched library with 25 μ L HiFi HotStart Taq (Kapa Biosystems), 5 μ L of Illumina TruSeq primer mix (5 μ M forward and reverse primers) and 5 μ L of ddH₂O. Post-enrichment PCR used the following thermal profile: 98 °C for 45 s; 18 cycles of 98 °C for 15 s, 60 °C for 30 s, 72 °C for 60 s; and a final extension of 72 °C for 5 m. We purified the resulting reactions using 1X bead clean using Kapa Pure Beads (Kapa Biosystems), and resuspended the enriched pools to total 22 μ L.

We then quantified pools using qPCR library quantification (Kapa Biosystems) with two serial dilutions of each pool (1:100,000, 1:1,000,000), assuming an average library fragment length of 600 bp. Based on the size-adjusted concentrations estimated by qPCR, we combined all pools at an equimolar concentration of 30 nM, and size selected for 250– 600 bp with a BluePippin (SageScience). We sequenced the pooled libraries in a single lane of a paired-end run on an Illumina HiSeq 2500 (2x150bp rapid run) at the University of Utah Huntsman Cancer Institute, or an Illumina NovaSeq 6000 (2x150 bp) at the University of Wisconsin-Madison.

Extracting UCEs from transcriptomic data

To reconcile the UCE dataset with RNASeq datasets, we followed the assembly, sanitation and reading frame detection pipeline as in Fernández et al. (2018) for assembling the transcriptomes. Additionally, we ran the Perl script for Rcorrector (Song and Florea, 2015) for error correction and downstream efficiency prior to assembly. FASTA files of transcriptomes resulting from CD-HIT-EST were converted to 2bit format using faToTwoBit, (Kent et al. 2002). In the PHYLUCE environment (publicly available at <https://phyluce.readthedocs.io/en/latest/tutorial-three.html>), we created a temporary relational database to summarize probe to assembly match using: *phyluce_probe_run_multiple_lastzs_sqlite* function on the 2bit files. The ultraconserved loci were recovered by the

phyluce_probe_slice_sequence_from_genomes command. The resulting FASTA files were treated as contigs and used to match the reads to the Blended probe set of Maddison et al. (2020).

Inclusion of Sanger-sequenced Terminals

To obtain a comprehensive phylogenetic framework, we compiled another matrix comprised of 109 terminals for six standard Sanger-sequenced loci. 12S ribosomal RNA (12S), 16S rRNA (16S), cytochrome c oxidase subunit 1 (COI), histone H3 (H3), and the small and large subunits of nuclear ribosomal genes (18S ribosomal rRNA (18S) and 28S ribosomal rRNA (28S), respectively). We integrated this data set by querying the raw files of the UCE data set for any potential match with 18S and 28S. Finally, COI and H3 markers were aligned with peptide translation using MACSE (Ranwez et al. 2011), with the invertebrate mitochondrial code implemented for COI. The remaining markers (12S, 16S, 18S and 28S) were aligned using MAFFT version 7 (Kato and Standley 2013). Trimming was performed on all alignments using trimAL (Capella-Gutiérrez et al. 2009) with *-gappyout*.

Phylogenomic Dating

We optimized the fossil information-based calibrations on a matrix comprising smallest UCE matrix (selected for highest taxon occupancy), plus the six Sanger loci. The maximum likelihood tree topology inferred for this dataset served as the basis for divergence time estimation, implementing uniform node age priors to accommodate the scarcity of terrestrial chelicerate fossils. The root age was set to a range of 545 Ma to 435 M, based on the age of *Eramoscorpius brucensis*, the oldest known arachnospulmonate. *Weygoldtina anglica*, the oldest known stem-Paleoamblypygi, was used to constrain the most recent common ancestor (MRCA) of crown Amblypygi. The Cretaceous fossils *Kronocharon prendinii* and *Britopygus weygoldtii* were assigned to the MRCA of (Charinidae + Charontidae) and (Phrynidae + Phrynichidae), respectively. Four other outgroup nodes were calibrated using the oldest unambiguous fossils representing those clades. Justifications and references for node calibrations are provided in Supplementary Table S3. Both chains were run for 20,000 generations, with an additional 5% set for burnin. We used the independent rates clock model for all partitions and all analyses were run using the same *seed* value (arbitrarily set to 5) to make the results reproducible.

Separately, we inferred divergence times under a penalized likelihood approach, as implemented in LSD2, which uses a least-squares approach based on a Gaussian model and is robust to uncorrelated violations of the molecular clock (To et al. 2016). The root age was set to a maximum of 545 Ma (Supplementary Table S3). We used the commands *prime* and *thorough* to optimize the analyses, and cross validation was used to select the optimal smoothing parameter. Following Eberle et al.

(2018), penalized likelihood optimization iterations were increased from the default of 2 to 5, and the number of penalized likelihood simulated annealing was doubled from 5,000 to 10,000. LSD2 requires at least one fixed date, so we used 314.6 Ma as a fixed date for the most recent common ancestor of *Scorpiões*.

Influence of the relict Paracharon on divergence time estimation

We compared the median age and variance of nodes between runs to assess which parts of the chronogram were most prone to node age overestimation. In addition, to compare the significance of sampling *Paracharon* versus ingroup fossil calibrations, we performed a third family of analyses wherein we retained all terminals but removed the three ingroup fossil node calibrations and kept only the five calibration points for outgroups.

Biogeography

We retained only the taxa of interest (*Amblypygi*) and the other outgroups terminals were pruned, following the recommendation to remove outgroup taxa by the authors of RASP (Yu et al., 2020). Dispersals were allowed between all regions at any time. Maximum range size was constrained to seven areas (allowing all areas). We evaluated the fit of our data to three distinct biogeographic models (DEC (Ree and Smith, 2008), DIVALIKE (Matzke, 2013) and BAYAREALIKE) with a combination of the jump parameter using likelihood ratio tests based on Akaike information criterion corrected for small sample sizes (AICc). To address the influence of *Paracharon* on ancestral states, we included two more independent analyses where, (i) we coded *Paracharon* as Neotropical+Africa to represent our sampling from Colombia and the *Paracharon* known from Guinea-Bissau; (ii) *Paracharon* excluded. We coded the areas based on the continental plates that delineate the extant distribution of *Amblypygi* groups: Africa, Australasia, Mediterranean, Nearctic, Neotropics, Oriental and Sundaland.

References

- Faircloth B.C. & Glenn T.C. 2012. Not all sequence tags are created equal: designing and validating sequence identification tags robust to indels. *PLoS One* 7:e42543. 10.1371/journal.pone.0042543.
- Yu Y., Blair C., He X.J. 2020. RASP 4: ancestral state reconstruction Tool for multiple genes and characters. *Mol. Biol. Evol.* 37:604–606.

Supplementary Table S1. Extant diversity of phylogenetic relicts within Chelicerata that constitute sister groups to extant orders.

Relict	Parent	Relict species	Non-relict sister species	Parent species	Proportion
Mesothelae	Araneae	182	49818	50000	0.00364
Cyphophthalmi	Opiliones	180	6339	6519	0.0276116
Austrodecidae	Pycnogonida	75	1255	1330	0.05639098
Opilioacariformes	Parasitiformes	37	12347	12384	0.00298773
Protoschizomidae	Schizomida	11	253	264	0.04166667
Prokoeneniidae	Palpigradi	7	75	82	0.08536585
Nanorchestidae	Acariformes	2	42231	42233	4.7356E-05
Paracharontidae	Amblypygi	1	259	260	0.00384615

Supplementary Table S2. Locality and accession data for terminals included in the study. Nuclear histone 3, H3; mitochondrial cytochrome c oxidase subunit I, COI; nuclear 28S rDNA, 28S; nuclear 18S rDNA, 18S; mitochondrial 16S rDNA, 16S; mitochondrial 12S rDNA, 12S

Voucher codes	Sequencing success - GenBank Acc.	Chime ra	Taxon, author	Locality
	SRX815750	No	<i>Pandinus imperator</i> (Koch, 1842)	Africa
	SRR3932806	No	<i>Centruroides sculpturatus</i> (Wood, 1863)	California, Arizona, New Mexico
	SRX815898	No	<i>Chaerilus celebensis</i> (Pocock, 1894)	Indonesia, Luwu
	SRX450965	No	<i>Liphistius malayanus</i> Abraham, 1923	Malaysia
	GCA_000661875	No	<i>Acanthoscurria geniculata</i> (Koch, 1841)	Brazil
ARALP000154/ ARALP000069	H3-KY018462 COI-KY017961 28S- KY017406 18S-KY016748 16S-KY016154 12S-KY015604	No	<i>Typopeltis crucifer</i> Pocock, 1894	Japan, Taiwan
MNHN-JAA17/ ARALP000013/ LP 3509	H3-FJ862878 28S-JN018408 18S- AF005446 16S-KY016153 12S-KY509342	Yes	<i>Mastigoproctus giganteus</i> (Pocock, 1894)	Mexico, USA
MNHN-JAC98	COI-JN018215 (part)	Yes	<i>Mastigoproctus giganteus</i> (Pocock, 1894)	Mexico, USA

ARALP000174	COI-KY017960 (part)	Yes	<i>Mastigoproctus giganteus</i> (Pocock, 1894)	Mexico, USA
ARALP000172	COI-KY017959 18S-KY016746 16S-KY016152	No	<i>Etienneus africanus</i> (Hentschel, 1899)	Gambia, Senegal
MCZ IZ-129084/TH01	COI-KY573153 28S-KP276369 18S-KY573511	No	<i>Thelyphonellus amazonicus</i> Butler, 1872	Brazil, Surinam
AMNH-LP14518	COI-MN103943 28S-MN108254 12S-MN108252	No	<i>Protoschizomus pachypalpus</i> (Rowland, 1973)	Mexico
AMNH-LP3755/ AMNH-LP6014/ FL47.2	COI-MN097762 18S-AF005444 16S-MN999751 12S-KY573465	No	<i>Stenochrus portoricensis</i> (Chamberlin, 1922)	Central America, South America, North America,
CASENT 9060741	UCE, this study	No	Schizo Tanzania	Tanzani, Eastern Arc Mountains
ARALP000138/ ARALP000003/ AMNH-LP3757	H3-KY018263 COI-KY017755 28S-KY017130 18S-KY509361 12S-MK849658	No	<i>Stenochrus sbordonii</i> (Brignoli, 1973)	Mexico
CASENT 9060721	UCE, this study	No	SchizoSaoTome_Principe	Sao Tome and Principe
MNRJ	UCE, this study	No	<i>Paracharon</i> sp.	Colombia
AMCC 124710	H3-AY829961 28S-AY829921 18S-AY829900 16S-AY829879 12S-AY829860	No	<i>Xerophrynus machadoi</i> (Fage, 1951)	Angola, Namibia
ARP-2015	28S-KP276346 18S-KP276426	No	<i>Trichodamon princeps</i> (Mello-Leitão, 1935)	Brazil

AMCC 124712	H3-AY829962 COI-AY829942 28S-AY829922 18S-AY829901 16S-AY829880 12S-AY829861	No	<i>Phrynichus scaber</i> (Gervais, 1844)	Mauritius, Seychelles
AMCC 124711	H3-AY829963 COI-AY829943 28S-AY829923 18S-AY829902 16S-AY829881 12S-AY829862	No	<i>Euphrynichus bacillifer</i> (Gerstaecker, 1873)	East Africa
MNHN-JAA1/ MNHN-JAB13	COI-JN018195 28S-JN018330 18S-JN018233	No	<i>Phrynichus orientalis</i> Weygoldt, 1998	Cambodia, Malaysia, Thailand, Vietnam
AMCC 124713	H3-AY829965 COI-AY829944 28S-AY829925 18S-AY829904 16S-AY829883 12S-AY829864	No	<i>Phrynichodamon scullyi</i> (Purcell, 1902)	South Africa
MNHN-JAB60/ AMCC 124715	28S-JN018405 18S-JN018308 16S-AY829884	Yes	<i>Damon medius</i> (Herbst, 1797)	Africa
MNHN-JAB60	COI-JN018192 (part)	Yes	<i>Damon medius</i> (Herbst, 1797)	Africa
AMCC 124715	COI-AY829945 (part)	Yes	<i>Damon medius</i> (Herbst, 1797)	Africa
AMCC 124714	H3-AY829964 28S-AY829924 18S-AY829903 16S-AY829882 12S-AY829863	No	<i>Musicodamon atlanteus</i> Fage, 1939	Algeria, Morocco
MNHN-JAD13	COI-JN018115 28S-JN018329 18S-JN018232	No	<i>Damon johnstoni</i> (Lydekker, 1879)	Africa
AMCC 124724	COI-AY829952 28S-AY829933 18S-AY829912 16S-AY829891 12S-AY829872	No	<i>Damon sylviae</i> Prendini, Weygoldt & Wheeler, 2005	Namibia
AMCC 124730/ AMCC 124725/ AMCC124727	H3-AY829979 COI-AY829958 28S-AY829939 18S-AY829918 16S-AY829892 12S-AY829874	No	<i>Damon variegatus</i> (Perty, 1834)	Africa

ARALP000030/ AMCC 124716/ AMCC 124717	H3-KY018357 COI-AY829946 28S- KY017271 18S-AY829907 16S-AY829886 12S-AY829866	No	<i>Damon diadema</i> (Simon, 1876)	Africa
AMCC 124718/ AMCC 124720/ AMCC 124719	COI-AY829948 28S-AY829931 18S- AY829910 16S-AY829888 12S-AY829869	No	<i>Damon annulatipes</i> (Wood, 1869)	South Africa
AMCC 124722/ MNHN-JAB38/ AMCC 124721	H3-AY829981 28S-JN018328 18S- AY829920 16S-AY829899 12S-AY829878	Yes	<i>Damon gracilis</i> Weygoldt, 1998	Angola, Namibia
MNHN-JAB38	COI-JN018114 (part)	Yes	<i>Damon gracilis</i> Weygoldt, 1998	Angola, Namibia
AMCC 124721	COI-AY829959 (part)	Yes	<i>Damon gracilis</i> Weygoldt, 1998	Angola, Namibia
Hb-B-CRdM- UFMG15422	COI-MT899143 (part)	No	<i>Heterophrynus batesii</i> (Butler, 1873)	Brazil
CMB 086	UCE, this study	No	<i>Heterophrynus</i> sp.1	Brazil, Amazonas, Guajará
AMCC_LP_3830/ MNHN-JAD3	COI-MW410162 28S-JN018333 18S- JN018236	No	<i>Heterophrynus</i> cf. <i>longicornis</i> (Butler, 1873)	French Guiana: Approuague-Kaw,Kaw mountains
MNHN-JAA81	COI-JN018118 28S-JN018332 18S- JN018235	No	<i>Heterophrynus alces</i> (Pocock, 1902)	Brazil, Guyana, Surinam
CHNUFPI 2141	UCE, this study	No	<i>Heterophrynus</i> <i>origami</i> Chirivi-Joya, Moreno-González & Fagua, 2020	Brazil, Rondonia, Jamari
CMB 083	UCE, this study	No	<i>Heterophrynus</i> sp.2	Brazil, Amazonas, Canutama
CMB 090	UCE this study	No	<i>Heterophrynus</i> sp.3	Brazil, Amazonas, Canutama

ARALP000188/ LP 1483/ ARALP000107 13872	H3-KY018358 COI-MT040911 28S- KY017272 18S-KY509344 16S-MF806089 12S-MF806134 COI-MT738756 28S-MT734793 18S- MT734777 16S-MT734766 12S-MT753022	No	<i>Phrynus longipes</i> (Pocock, 1894)	Dominican Republic, Haiti, Puerto Rico, Virgin Islands
13881	COI-MT738757 28S-MT734794 18S- MT734778 16S-MT734767	No	<i>Paraphrynus</i> <i>viridiceps</i> (Pocock, 1894)	The Bahamas, Cuba
AMCC_LP_16891/ AMCC_LP_5374/ AMCC_LP_16893 AMCC_LP_8672	COI-MW410159 28S-MW411456 16S- MW411542 18S-MW411509 (part)	Yes	<i>Acanthophrynus</i> <i>coronatus</i> (Butler, 1873)	Mexico, USA
AMCC_LP_16886	18S-MW411499 (part)	Yes	<i>Acanthophrynus</i> <i>coronatus</i> (Butler, 1873)	Mexico, USA
AMCC_LP_8672	18S-MW411485 (part)	Yes	<i>Acanthophrynus</i> <i>coronatus</i> (Butler, 1873)	Mexico, USA
AMCC_LP_5374	12S-MW411482 (part)	Yes	<i>Acanthophrynus</i> <i>coronatus</i> (Butler, 1873)	Mexico, USA
AMCC_LP_16886	12S-MW411499 (part)	Yes	<i>Acanthophrynus</i> <i>coronatus</i> (Butler, 1873)	Mexico, USA

14072	18S-MT734779 16S-MT734768 12S-MT753024	Yes	<i>Phrynus marginemaculatus</i> (C. L. Koch, 1841)	The Bahamas, Bermuda, Cayman Islands, Cuba, Dominican Republic, Haiti, Jamaica, Puerto Rico, USA
80122	COI-MH478994 (part)	Yes	<i>Phrynus marginemaculatus</i> (C. L. Koch, 1841)	The Bahamas, Bermuda, Cayman Islands, Cuba, Dominican Republic, Haiti, Jamaica, Puerto Rico, USA
14072	COI-MT738758 (part)	Yes	<i>Phrynus marginemaculatus</i> (C. L. Koch, 1841)	The Bahamas, Bermuda, Cayman Islands, Cuba, Dominican Republic, Haiti, Jamaica, Puerto Rico, USA
AMNH	UCE, this study	No	<i>Paraphrynus raptator</i> (Pocock, 1902)	Honduras, Dept. Comayagua, Meambar
USNM AH5XA82	UCE, this study	No	<i>Paraphrynus</i> sp.1	Costa Rica, Heredia, Puerto Viejo de Sarapiquí
USNM AH5XA88	UCE, this study	No	<i>Phrynus</i> sp.1	Costa Rica, Heredia
AMCC_LP_6145	COI-MW410163 28S-MW411480 18S-MW411515 16S-MW411544 12S-MW411573	No	<i>Paraphrynus laevifrons</i> (Pocock, 1894)	Costa Rica, Puntarenas Province, Fundacion Neotropica
USNM AH5AX88	UCE, this study	No	<i>Phrynus</i> sp.2	Costa Rica, Heredia
14444	COI-MT738750 28S-MT734787 18S-MT734771 16S-MT734760 12S-MT753016	No	<i>Paraphrynus carolynae</i> de Armas, 2012	Mexico, USA
2091	COI-MT738753 28S-MT734790 18S-MT734774 16S-MT734763 12S-MT753019	No	<i>Paraphrynus pococki</i> Mullinex, 1975	Mexico
8667	COI-MT738749 28S-MT734786 18S-MT734770 12S-MT753015	No	<i>Paraphrynus baeops</i> Mullinex, 1975	Mexico
15431	COI-MT738752 28S-MT734789 18S-MT734773 16S-MT734762 12S-MT753018	No	<i>Paraphrynus mexicanus</i> (Bilimek, 1867)	Mexico

2096	COI-MT738748 28S-MT734785 18S-MT734769 16S-MT734759 12S-MT753014	No	<i>Paraphrynus aztecus</i> (Pocock, 1894)	Mexico
13883	COI-MT738751 28S-MT734788 18S-MT734772 16S-MT734761 12S-MT753017	No	<i>Paraphrynus cubensis</i> (Quintero, 1983)	Cuba
LP 11377/ LP 11375	COI-MT040904 28S-KY509389 18S-KY509339 16S-MF806085 12S-MF806128	No	<i>Weygoldtia davidovi</i> (Fage, 1946)	Cambodia, Laos, Vietnam
LP 11269	COI-MT040912 28S-KY509395 18S-KY509345 16S-MF806090 12S-MF806135	No	<i>Weygoldtia consonensis</i> Miranda, Giupponi, Prendini & Scharff, 2021	Con Son Island
MNHN-JAA93	COI-JN018111 28S-JN018325 18S-JN018228	No	<i>Catageus</i> sp.1	Unknown
MNHN-JAB1	COI-JN018112 28S-JN018326 18S-JN018229	No	<i>Catageus</i> sp.2	Unknown
LP 9074	COI-MT040928 28S-KY509413 18S-KY509363 16S-MF806105 MF806153	No	<i>Sarax seychellarum</i> (Kraepelin, 1898)	Seychelles
LP 13394/ LP2843	COI-MT040910 28S-KY509393 18S-KY509343 16S-MF806088 12S-MF806133	No	<i>Sarax ioanniticus</i> (Kritscher, 1959)	Egypt, Greece, Jordan, Israel, Italy, Turkey
	SRX8887651-SRX8887663	No	<i>Sarax israelensis</i> (Miranda, Aharon, Gavish-Regev, Giupponi & Wizen, 2016)	Israel
LP 12169/ LP 12123	COI-MT040945 28S-KY509430 18S-KY509380 16S-MF806116 12S-MF806167	No	<i>Sarax yayukae</i> Rahmadi, Harvey & Kojima, 2010	Sabah, Sarawak - Malaysia

LP 4761	COI-MT040931 28S-KY509416 18S-KY509366 16S-MF806107 12S-MF806156	No	<i>Sarax singaporeae</i> (Gravely, 1911)	Singaporeae
LP 11594	COI-MT040925 28S-MF806103 18S-MF806150 16S-KY509410 12S-KY509360	No	<i>Sarax</i> sp. Bali	Indonesia, Bali
LP 1926	COI-MT040900 28S-KY509385 18S-KY509335 16S-MF806081 12S-MF806124	No	<i>Sarax brachydactylus</i> Simon, 1892	Philippines
LP 5564	COI-MT040913 28S-MF806091 18S - MF806137; 16S -KY509397; 12S - KY509347	No	<i>Sarax bilua</i> Miranda, Prendini, Giupponi & Scharff, 2021	Solomon Islands
LP 13118	COI-MT040902 28S-KY509387 18S - KY509337; 16S - MF806083; 12S - MF806126	No	<i>Sarax cochinensis</i> (Gravely, 1915)	Kerala - India
LP 12298	COI-MT040899 28S-KY509384 18S-KY509334 16S-MF806080 12S-MF806123	No	<i>Sarax bispinosus</i> (Nair, 1934)	India, Sri Lanka
MNHN-JAC60	COI-MT040899 28S-KY509384 18S-KY509334 16S-MF806080 12S-MF806123	No	<i>Catageus</i> sp.3	Unknown
MR365 (unregistered)	UCE, this study	No	<i>Charon</i> sp.	Torres Strait: Dauan Island
MNHN-JAA95	COI-JN018110 28S-JN018324 18S-JN018227	No	<i>Sarax</i> sp.	Unknown
LP 11998	COI-MT040935 28S-MF806109 18S-MF806160 16S-KY509420 12S-KY509370	No	<i>Sarax tiomanensis</i> Miranda, Prendini, Giupponi & Scharff, 2021	Tioman Island - Malaysia
LP 11997	COI-MT040924 28S-KY509409 18S-KY509359 16S-MF806102 12S-MF806149	No	<i>Sarax rimosus</i> (Simon, 1901)	Malaysia, Singaporeae

LP 1927	COI-MT040898 28S-KY509383 18S-KY509333 16S-MF806079 12S-MF806122	No	<i>Sarax batuensis</i> Roewer, 1962	Batu Caves
MNRJ	UCE, this study	No	<i>Charinus diamantinus</i> Miranda, Prendini, Giupponi & Scharff, 2021	caves of Diamantina Plateau - Brazil
LP 10076	COI-MT040903 28S-KY509388 18S-KY509338 16S-MF806084 12S-MF806127	No	<i>Charinus gertschi</i> Goodnight & Goodnight, 1946	Guyana, Surinam, Venezuela
LP 13448	COI-MT040929 28S-KY509414 18S-KY509364 12S-MF806154	No	<i>Charinus sillami</i> Réveillion & Maquart, 2015	French Guyana
LP 3831	COI-MT040917 28S-KY509401 18S-KY509351 16S-MF806095 12S-MF806141	No	<i>Charinus palikur</i> Miranda, Prendini, Giupponi & Scharff, 2021	French Guiana, Roura
LP 6943	COI-MT040897 28S-KY509382 18S-KY509332 16S-MF806078 12S-MF806121	No	<i>Charinus africanus</i> (Hansen, 1921)	Equatorial Guinea, São Tomé and Príncipe
ZMH: A0000893	COI-MH107031	No	<i>Charinus kakum</i> Harms, 2018	Kakum National Park - Ghana
LP 13396	COI-MT040939 28S-KY509424 18S-KY509374 16S-MF806113 12S-MF806164	No	<i>Charinus vulgaris</i> Miranda & Giupponi, 2011	Porto Velho - Rondonia, Salvador - Bahia - Brazil
USNMENT 1458725	UCE, this study	No	<i>Charinus</i> sp.2	Brazil, Pernambuco, Recife

LP 10473	COI-MT040906 28S-KY509390 18S-KY509340 12S-MF806129	No	<i>Charinus dominicanus</i> Armas & Pérez, 2001	Dominican Republic
LP 10170	COI-MT040938 28S-KY509423 18S-KY509373 16S-MF806112 12S-MF806163	No	<i>Charinus aguayoi</i> Moyá-Guzman, 2009	Puerto Rico
	SRX10297721	No	<i>Charinus acosta</i> (Quintero, 1983)	Cuba
LP 13402	COI-MT040922 28S-KY509407 18S-KY509357 16S-MF806100 12S-MF806147	No	<i>Charinus reddelli</i> Miranda, Giupponi & Wizen, 2016	Footprint Cave and Waterfall Cave - Belize
UFPI 11323	UCE, this study	No	<i>Charinus carvalhoi</i> Miranda, Prendini, Giupponi & Scharff, 2021	Roraima - Brazil
MNRJ	UCE, this study	No	<i>Charinus magalhaesi</i> Miranda, Prendini, Giupponi & Scharff, 2021	Amazonas, Manaus - Brazil
LP 6366	COI-MT040920 28S-KY509405 18S-KY509355 16S-MF806099 12S-MF806145	No	<i>Charinus pescotti</i> Dunn, 1949	Australia, Queensland
ARALP000157/ LP 10276/ LP 5174	H3-KY018133 COI-MT040916 28S-KY509400 18S-KY509350 16S-MF806093 12S-MF806139	No	<i>Charinus neocaledonicus</i> Kraepelin, 1895	New Caledonia
LP 5175	28S-KY509391 18S-KY509341 16S-MF806086 12S-MF806130	No	<i>Charinus elegans</i> (Weygoldt, 2006)	New Caledonia
USNMENT 1458727	UCE, this study	No	<i>Charinus una</i> Miranda, Prendini,	Brazil, Bahia

				Giupponi & Scharff, 2021	
LP 13400	COI-MT040934 28S-KY509419 18S- KY509369 12S-MF806159	No		<i>Charinus taboa</i> Vasconcelos, Giupponi & Ferreira, 2016	Brazil, Minas Gerais
Charinus_6.3 Roc	COI-MK801767 16S-MK810724	No		<i>Charinus rocamadre</i> Torres-Contreras, García & Armas, 2015	Colombia, Sucre
MNRJ 9366	UCE, this study	No		<i>Charinus montanus</i> Weygoldt, 1972	Brazil, Espírito Santo
AM7	28S-KP276344 18S-KP276424	No		<i>Charinus asturius</i> Pinto-da-Rocha, Machado & Weygoldt, 2002	Brazil, São Paulo
USNMENT014081 66	UCE, this study	No		<i>Charinus euclidesi</i> Miranda, Prendini, Giupponi & Scharff, 2021	Brazil, Rio de Janeiro
MNRJ	UCE, this study	No		<i>Charinus caatingae</i> Vasconcelos & Ferreira, 2016	Brazil, Bahia
LP 13398	COI-MT040921 28S-KY509406 18S- KY509356 12S-MF806146	No		<i>Charinus potiguar</i> Vasconcelos, Giupponi & Ferreira, 2013	Brazil, Rio Grande do Norte
MNRJ	UCE, this study	No		<i>Charinus cf potiguar</i>	Brazil, Rio Grande do Norte

USNMENT014081 54	UCE, this study	No	<i>Charinus souzai</i> Miranda, Prendini, Giupponi & Scharff, 2021	Brazil, Espírito Santo
USNMENT014081 53	UCE, this study	No	<i>Charinus sooretama</i> Miranda, Prendini, Giupponi & Scharff, 2021	Brazil, Espírito Santo
USNMENT015803 25	UCE, this study	No	<i>Charinus</i> sp.1	Brazil, Espírito Santo
MNRJ 9363	UCE, this study	No	<i>Charinus brasilianus</i> Weygoldt, 1972	Brazil, Espírito Santo
USNMENT015803 22	UCE, this study	No	<i>Charinus</i> sp.3	Brazil, Espírito Santo
MNRJ 9362	UCE, this study	No	<i>Charinus ruschii</i> Miranda, Milleri-Pinto, Gonçalves-Souza, Giupponi & Scharff, 2016	Brazil, Espírito Santo
USNMENT014082 05	UCE, this study	No	<i>Charinus goitaca</i> Miranda, Prendini, Giupponi & Scharff, 2021	Brazil, Rio de Janeiro
USNMENT015803 27	UCE, this study	No	<i>Charinus</i> sp.	Brazil, Espírito Santo
WAM	UCE, this study	Yes	<i>Charon</i> sp.	

Supplementary Table S3. Fossil calibrations and references for divergence time estimation.

Node	Fossil	Taxonomy	Calibration	Node calibrated	Reference
Root	<i>Eramoscorpis brucensis</i>	Scorpiones (stem-group)	435 Mya (lower) to 545 (upper)	Root	Waddington et al. 2015
Crown Scorpiones	<i>Compsoscorpis buthiformis</i>	Scorpiones, crown Orthosterni	314.6 (lower)	MRCA (Scorpiones)	Pointon et al. 2012
Crown Araneae	<i>Palaeothele montceauensis</i>	Araneae, stem-Mesothelae	299 (lower)	MRCA (Araneae)	Selden 1996
Crown Uropygi	<i>Parageralinura naufraga</i>	Thelyphonida, stem-Uropygi	319 (lower)	MRCA (Thelyphonida)	Brauckman and Kock 1983
Crown Tetrapulmonata	<i>Attercopus fimbriunguis</i>	Uraraneida	374 (lower)	MRCA (Tetrapulmonata)	Selden et al. 2008
Crown Amblypygi	<i>Weygoldtina angelica</i>	Amblypygi, stem-Palaeoamblypygi	313.7 (lower)	MRCA (Amblypygi)	Pocock 1911
Crown Charontida	<i>Kronocharon prendinii</i>	Amblypygi, Charontida	105 (lower)	MRCA (Charontida)	Grimaldi and Engel 2014
Crown Phrynida	<i>Britopygus weygoldti</i>	Amblypygi, Phrynida	112 (lower)	MRCA (Phrynida)	Dunlop and Martill 2002

Supplementary Table S4. Concatenation of UCE and six-marker data set.

Sanger names	UCE names
Acanthophrynus_coronatus	Acanthophrynus_coronatus
Catageus_sp1	
Catageus_sp2	
Catageus_sp3	
Centruroides_sculpturatus_AR105	Centruroides_sculpturatus_AR105
Chaerilus_celebensis	Chaerilus_celebensis
Charinus_acosta	Charinus_acosta
Charinus_africanus	
Charinus_aguayoi	
Charinus_asturius	Charinus_asturius_GSM243
Charinus_brasilianus_GSM159	Charinus_brasilianus_GSM159
Charinus_caatingae_GSM373	caatingaeGSM373
Charinus_carvalhoi	
Charinus_diamantinus3762	charinus_diamantinusgsm376_2
Charinus_dominicanus	
Charinus_elegans	
Charinus_euclidesi_GSM257	Charinus_euclidesi_GSM257
Charinus_gertschi	
Charinus_goitaca_GSM133	Charinus_goitaca_GSM133
Charinus_kakum	
Charinus_magalhaesi	Charinus_magalhaesi_GSM394
Charinus_montanus_GSM123	Charinus_montanus_GSM123
Charinus_neocaledonicus	
Charinus_palikur	
Charinus_pescotti	
Charinus_potiguar_GSM371	Charinus_potiguar_GSM371
Charinus_reddelli	
Charinus_rocamadre	
Charinus_ruschii_GSM240	Charinus_ruschii_GSM240
Charinus_seychellarum	Charinus_seychellarum_GSM413
Charinus_sillami	
Charinus_sooretama_GSM233	Charinus_sooretama_GSM233
Charinus_souzai_GSM231	Charinus_souzai_GSM231
Charinus_sp._1196	Charinus_sp._1196
Charinus_sp1_GSM173	Charinus_sp1_GSM173
Charinus_sp2_GSM386	Charinus_sp2_GSM386

Charinus_sp3_1181	Charinus_sp3_1181
Charinus_taboa	
Charinus_vulgaris	Charinus_vulgaris_GSM391
Charon_CMB043	Charon_sp._CMB043
Damon_annulatipes	
Damon_diadema	
Damon_gracilis	
Damon_johnstonii	
Damon_medius	
Damon_sylviae	
Etienneus_africanus	
Euphrynichus_bacillifer	Euphrynichus_bacillifer_clean
Heterophrynus_alces	
Heterophrynus_batesii	
Heterophrynus_longicornis	
Heterophrynus_origami_CHNUFPI2141_C MB085	Heterophrynus_origami_CHNUFPI2141_C MB085
Heterophrynus_sp._CHNUFPI2271_CMB0 90	Heterophrynus_sp._CHNUFPI2271_CMB0 90
Heterophrynus_sp._CMB083	Heterophrynus_sp._CMB083
Liphistius_malayanus	Liphistius_yangae
Mastigoproctus_giganteus	Mastigoproctus_giganteus
Musicodamon_atlanteus	Musicodamon_atlanteus_GSM416-et-422
Pandinus_imperator	Pandinus_imperator
Paracharon_sp._GSM424	Paracharon_sp._GSM424
Paraphrynus_aztecus	
Paraphrynus_baeops	
Paraphrynus_carolynae	
Paraphrynus_cubensis	
Paraphrynus_laevifrons	
Paraphrynus_mexicanus	
Paraphrynus_pococki	
Paraphrynus_raptator_GSM414	Paraphrynus_raptator_GSM414
Paraphrynus_robustus	
Paraphrynus_sp._AH5XA82	Paraphrynus_sp._AH5XA82
Paraphrynus_viridiceps	
Phrynichodamon_scullyi	
Phrynichus_orientalis	

Phrynichus_scaber	
Phrynus_longipes	
Phrynus_marginemaculatus	Phrynus_marginemaculatus
Phrynus_sp._AH5XA68	Phrynus_sp._AH5XA68
PhrynusAH5AX68	
Protoschizomus_pachypalpus	
Sarax_batuensis	
Sarax_bilua	
Sarax_brachydactylus	
Sarax_buxtoni	
Sarax_cochinensis	
Sarax_cochinensis_bispinosus	
Sarax_ioanniticus	Sarax_ioanniticus
Sarax_israelensis	Sarax_israelensis
Sarax_rimosus	
Sarax_singaporeae	
Sarax_sp_Bali	
Sarax_sp_JA2011	
Sarax_tiomanensis	
Sarax_yayukae	
Schizomida_undet_SaoTome_Principe_GS M438	Schizomida_undet_SaoTome_Principe_GS M438
Schizomida_undet_Tanzania_GSM445	Schizomida_undet_Tanzania_GSM445
Stenochrus_portoricensis	Stenochrus_sp._IZ74289
Stenochrus_sbordonii	
Thelyphonellus_amazonicus	
Trichodamon_princeps	Trichodamon_princeps_GSM423
Typopeltis_crucifer	
unaGSM381	Charinus_una_GSM381
Weygoldtia_consonensis	
Weygoldtia_davidovi	
Xerophrynus_machadoi	
	Acanthoscurria_geniculata
	Heterophrynus_longicornis_CHNUFPI2142
	Heterophrynus_sp._CMB086

Table S . rea ing eme ue r bi ge grap i analy i .

Ta n	State
Acanthophrinus_coronatus	Nearctic
Catageussp1	Oriental
Catageussp2	Oriental
Catageussp3	Oriental
Charinus_acosta	Neotropical
Charinus_africanus	Africa
Charinus_aguayoi	Neotropical
Charinus_asturius	Neotropical
Charinus_australianus_elegans	Australasia
Charinus_carvalhoi	Neotropical
Charinus_diamantinus3762	Neotropical
Charinus_dominicanus	Neotropical
Charinus_elegans	Australasia
Charinus_euclidesi	Neotropical
Charinus_gertschi	Neotropical
Charinus_goitaca	Neotropical
Charinus_kakum	Africa
Charinus_magalhaesi	Neotropical
Charinus_montanus_GSM123	Neotropical
Charinus_neocaledonicus	Australasia
Charinus_palikur	Neotropical
Charinus_pescotti	Australasia
Charinus_potiguar	Neotropical
Charinus_potiguar_2	Neotropical
Charinus_reddelli	Neotropical
Charinus_rocamadre	Neotropical
Charinus_ruschii	Neotropical
Charinus_seychellarum	Africa
Charinus_sillami	Neotropical
Charinus_sooretama_GSM233	Neotropical
Charinus_souzai_GSM231	Neotropical
Charinus_sp_1196	Neotropical
Charinus_sp1_GSM173	Neotropical
Charinus_sp2_GSM386	Neotropical
Charinus_sp3_1181	Neotropical
Charinus_taboa	Neotropical
Charinus_una	Neotropical
Charinus_vulgaris	Neotropical
Charnius_caatingae	Neotropical
Charon_CMB043	Australasia
Charon_WestAustMus	Australasia
Damon_annulatipes	Africa
Damon_diadema	Africa
Damon_gracilis	Africa

Damon_johnstonii	Africa
Damon_medius	Africa
Damon_sylviae	Africa
Damon_variegatus	Africa
Euphrynichus_bacillifer	Africa
Heterophrynus_alces	Africa
Heterophrynus_batesii	Africa
Heterophrynus_CMB083_3386	Neotropical
Heterophrynus_longicornis	Neotropical
Heterophrynus_origami_CHNUFPI2141_CMB085	Neotropical
Heterophrynus_sp_CHNUFPI2271_CMB090	Neotropical
Heterophrynus_sp_CMB086_2260	Neotropical
Musicodamon_atlanteus	Africa
Paracharon_sp_GSM424	Neotropical
Paraphrynus_aztecus	Neotropical
Paraphrynus_baeops	Neotropical
Paraphrynus_carolynae	Neotropical
Paraphrynus_cubensis	Neotropical
Paraphrynus_laevifrons	Neotropical
Paraphrynus_mexicanus	Neotropical
Paraphrynus_pococki	Neotropical
Paraphrynus_raptator_GSM414	Neotropical
Paraphrynus_robustus	Neotropical
Paraphrynus_sp_AH5XA82	Neotropical
Paraphrynus_viridiceps	Neotropical
Phrynichodamon_scullyi	Africa
Phrynichus_orientalis	Oriental
Phrynichus_scaber	Africa
Phrynus_longipes	Neotropical
Phrynus_marginemaculatus	Neotropical+Nearctic
Phrynus_sp_AH5XA68	Neotropical
Sarax_batuensis	Oriental
Sarax_bilua	Australasia
Sarax_brachydactylus	Oriental
Sarax_buxtoni	Oriental
Sarax_cochinensis	Oriental
Sarax_cochinensis_bispinosus	Oriental
Sarax_ioanniticus	Mediterranean
Sarax_israelensis	Mediterranean
Sarax_rimosus	Oriental
Sarax_singaporeae	Oriental
Sarax_sp_Bali	Sundaland
Sarax_sp_JA2011	Sundaland
Sarax_tiomansensis	Oriental
Sarax_yayukae	Oriental
Trichodamon_princeps	Neotropical
Weygoldtia_consonensis	Oriental
Weygoldtia_davidovi	Oriental
Xerophrynus_machadoi	Africa

Supplementary Table S6. Statistics of model comparison inferred from the RASP analysis.

	LnL	numparams	d	e	j	AICc	AICc_wt
DEC	-108.5	2	0.021	0.0074	0	221.1	1.40E-10
DEC+J	-84.81	3	0.0016	1.00E-12	0.016	175.9	0.89
DIVALIKE	-106.5	2	0.031	2.00E-09	0	217.2	9.50E-10
DIVALIKE+J	-86.93	3	0.0025	1.00E-12	0.018	180.1	0.11
BAYAREALIKE	-136.3	2	0.024	0.29	0	276.8	1.10E-22
BAYAREALIKE+J	-89.76	3	0.0021	1.00E-07	0.022	185.8	0.0063

Supplementary Table S7. i eli ood percentages of inferred ancestral areas using AS .Statistics of odel co mparison inferred fro t e AS anal sis. Area coding as follows: Nearctic-A; Oriental-B;Neotropical-C; Africa-D; Australasia-E; Mediterranean-F; Sundaland-G.

Node	Model	Area	Percentage
<i>Paracharon</i> coded as C			
Crown Amblypygi	DEC	BCDF	46.43
Crown Amblypygi	DEC+j	BCD	39.95
Crown Euamblypygi	DEC	BCDF	26.23
Crown Euamblypygi	DEC+j	BCD	26.94
Phrynichidae	DEC	D	69.38
Phrynichidae	DEC+j	D	95.43
Phrynidae	DEC	CD	72.81
Phrynidae	DEC+j	C	41.14
Charontidae	DEC	BDF	41.54
Charontidae	DEC+j	B	36.51
<i>Paracharon</i> excluded			
Crown Amblypygi	DEC	BDF	29.2
Crown Amblypygi	DEC+j	BCD	27.43
Crown Euamblypygi	DEC	BDF	29.2
Crown Euamblypygi	DEC+j	BCD	27.43
Phrynichidae	DEC	D	72.57
Phrynichidae	DEC+j	D	96.28
Phrynidae	DEC	CD	75.22
Phrynidae	DEC+j	C	38.22
Charontidae	DEC	BDF	44.43
Charontidae	DEC+j	B	40.81
<i>Paracharon</i> coded as CD			
Crown Amblypygi	DEC	BCDF	26.48
Crown Amblypygi	DEC+j	CD	69.87
Crown Euamblypygi	DEC	BDF	21.73
Crown Euamblypygi	DEC+j	D	61.89
Phrynichidae	DEC	D	73.99
Phrynichidae	DEC+j	D	98.02
Phrynidae	DEC	CD	76.94
Phrynidae	DEC+j	C	49.18
Charontidae	DEC	BDF	37.07
Charontidae	DEC+j	D	59.87

Figure S1a

Figure S1b

Figure S1c

Figure S1d

Figure S1e

Figure S1f

Figure S1g

0.06

Figure S1h

Figure S2.

Figure S3.

Figure S4.

Figure S5

Figure S6